

A Study on Women Consumer Purchasing Behaviour Towards Mobile phones in Thanjavur

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ABSTRACT

Consumer studies are an ongoing process and its difficult to bring out an unified conclusion, this is because consumer vary by taste, design, colour ,etc. consumer behavior reflects the totality of consumer's decisions with respect to acquisition, consumption and disposition of goods, service, time and idea by (human) decision making units (over time). An understanding of purchase behavior of women towards mobile phones is an essential as it reflects the influence of brands, price, quality, quantity, mode of purchase, etc. the success of the market or the failure depends on the purchase behavior of consumers. Women are taking the lead roles as of today than the yester years. This is due to the outcome of education, employment, etc. Present women are taking the lead in purchase decisions too. This study will show to find out the women consumer purchasing behavior and decision which helps to choose the mobile phone. The study focus on women purchasing behavior towards mobile handsets.

Key words: *women consumer, purchasing decision, mobile handset.*

Introduction

Man has adopted different means of communication over time. consumer studies are the ongoing process and it is difficult to bring out an unified conclusion this is because consumer is vary by design color, taste, etc. consumer behavior reflects the totality of consumer's decision with respect to acquisition, consumption and disposition of goods service, time and idea by human decision making units .it also includes whether ,why, when, where, how, how much and how often and how long consumer are the important dimension in the decision making process towards mobile phones used by the women consumer . In the competitive market, the prospective buyer is prepared to choose the right brand based on their needs. All purchase made by a consumer by following a certain decision making process. a consumer is one who does some physical activities and deliberates to take decisions concerning purchase and to dispose off on to evaluate products and services .In 21st Century the mobile phone support a wide range of services such as text message ,business application ,gaming short range wireless

communication internet ect .first mobile phone launch by Motorola in India. The beginning of mobile phone industry the first generation system used but it could not support to make more effective later 2Gand3G feature came in the market which make the boost in the market. India mobile industry is fastest growing in the world .India is the second largest mobile phone market after china. it has the world third -largest internet use base .the Indian market is dominated by various mobiles companies such as Samsung, sonny Ericson ,Xiaomi ,Motorola, apple, LG, micro max etc. the women consumer purchase decision influence in different factors through the world .this factor can be personality of customer and features associated with mobile phone handset. The customer preference of mobile phone attributes such as design, price, internet connection, battery life, gaming photo shooting, SMS, video quality, apps, downloading, and participants in large number. The product attributes helps to select the product when customer confused between different products .this study will show to find out the women consumer purchasing behavior and decision which helps to choose the mobile phone. The study will focus on women purchasing behavior and decision making towards mobile phones .

Review of Literature

Shanthi .r(2005) examined the perceptual dimension of brand association with reference to mobile users in Chennai city .shashi kumar sharma,l&chaubey, DS (2007) assessed the consumer the consumer awareness and their attitude toward different mobile service providers operating lucknow. gupta (1987) examined the factors motivating consumer to buy durables , the factors considers by them in making brand choice source of information considered , role of familes members in influencing brand choice and to examine consumer satisfaction (amritsar city) Amanda & hudal ,B.S (2007) examined the comparative buying behaviour of rural and their urban counterparts towards the purchasing of refrigerators. the factors considered by them : item of necessity , symbol of social status , advertismnt influencing brand reputation and time saving device.dr.sathya swaroopdebasish &dr nabaghan mallick (2015) examined the consumer buying behaviour of mobile hand set in odisha.

Statement of the Problem

Women are taking leading roles of today than yester years. The problem of this study shows the understanding of purchase behavior of women and how they are facing problems while making a decision to purchase mobile phones in the market. Because it reflects the influence of brands, price, quality, mode of purchase etc.

Scope of the study:

This study will make the available researches to provide the proper information about the women consumer purchasing behavior towards mobiles phones. And also this study is aimed to know the awareness of purchasing patterns of mobile phone among the women consumer.

Objective of the study

1. To study women's purchasing behavior towards mobile phones
2. To know the role of women in purchase decision making process.

3. To know the factors which influenced by women consumer to purchase particular brand of mobile handsets.

Research methodology

Research Design : Descriptive research design has been used for this study .Both Primary Data and Secondary source of data have been collected. Primary data has been collected by using structured questionnaire which was administered by personal interview and secondary data has been collected from books, journals, reports and websites.

Sample size : 125 women consumer has been taken for the study from Thanjavur.

Sampling procedure: The purpose of the study that respondents were selected from different places of the Thanjavur from different Occupations, Educational level, Income and Age groups. and Convenience sampling technique was used for collecting response from the respondents.

Statistical tools: simple percentage, chi-square, correlation analysis were used for this study.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table -1 Marital Status of the Study

Marital status	No.of respondents	Percentage
Married	100	80
Un Married	25	20
Total	125	100

Table -2 Source of Shop Awareness of Women Consumer

Source of shop awareness	No. of respondents	Percentage
Advertisement	60	48
Relatives and friends	35	28
Shopkeepers	15	12
Nearer to residence	15	12
Total	125	100

Table -3 Opinions about the Factors Influencing Women Consumer
Purchasing Behavior of Mobile Handsets

Influencing factors	No. of respondents	Percentage
Quality	50	40
Quantity	5	4
Cost	20	16
Service	5	4
Customer relation	5	4
Brand	40	32
Total	125	100

Table -4 Correlations between Marital Status Factors Influencing Women Consumer Purchasing Behavior of Mobile Handset

Influencing factors	No. of respondents		Percentage
	Married	Un Married	
Quality	45	5	50
Quantity	5	0	5
Cost	15	5	20
Service	5	0	5
Customer relation	25	15	40
Total	100	25	100

Findings, Suggestions and Conclusion

The various findings of the study are given in the following:

- Majority of the respondents (44.00%) are belonging to the age group of 21- 30 years
- Most of the consumers (28.00%) are H.Sc and Postgraduates.
- Majority of the consumers (40.00%) are Home makers.
- Majority of the consumers (60.00%) are Medium Size family.
- Most of the consumers (80.00%) are Married respondents in women
- Most of the women consumers (64.00%) are in urban area.
- Most of the women consumers (40.00%) are selecting Quality of products only.

SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

The motive behind conducting this study on women consumer purchasing behavior is to demystify the Approach of consumers while making buying decisions. Marketers always show their keen interest to know the likings and preferences of women consumers while visiting shopping stores and formulate strategies to make products accordingly. In order to cope with intense competition, marketers can utilize the current information about

behavior of their target customers in order to launch a new product or to reposition their existing product. If companies become successful in understanding the mindset of women consumers and make them buy their products then there would be immense chances for exponential growth for companies. Consumer behavior field in terms of their needs and wants as well their perception, attitude and personality including motivation and their rate of involvement is also vital not only for the marketers but also for the government and society as a whole. This study that the women consumer behavior remains an another cornerstone for the successful marketing.

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